

BROMINATION OF COMPOUNDS CONTAINING TWO AROMATIC
NUCLEI. PART VIII. BROMINATION OF ARYL ESTERS
OF 5-NITROSALICYLIC ACID

BY R. M. THAKKAR AND G. V. JADHAV

Phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-cresyl and *m*- and *p*-nitrophenyl esters of 5-nitrosalicylic acid have been brominated in acetic acid medium as well as with liquid bromine and the constitutions of bromination products have been proved by hydrolysis and confirmed by mixed melting points with synthetic products.

The present work was taken up with a view to studying the effect of the introduction of a negative group like NO₂ in the acidic part of aryl esters, already worked out by Thakkar and Jadhav (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1949, 18, III, 30) in the course of bromination. It has been observed that bromine enters only the acidic part of the molecule in presence of the solvent, whilst it enters the phenolic part only when liquid bromine is used. Bromination with liquid bromine in presence of a catalyst like iodine, however, gives compounds with bromine in both the parts.

Further, it was observed that introduction of a negative group like NO₂ in the phenolic part practically completely deactivated the molecule, as the ester was recovered unchanged when treated with liquid bromine, and the use of iodine catalyst could give, in the case of *p*-nitrophenyl 5-nitrosalicylate, a compound with bromine in the acidic part of the molecule.

The constitutions of the bromination products were arrived at by alkaline hydrolysis and confirmed by synthesis in most cases. In the case of the dibromo product of *p*-cresyl 5-nitrosalicylate and *p*-cresyl 3-bromo-5-nitrosalicylate, substances gave a definite lowering in melting point, when mixed with 2:6-dibromo-*p*-cresyl derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromination in Acetic Acid Medium.—The requisite ester (2 g.) was dissolved in hot acetic acid and 20% solution of bromine in acetic acid (15 c.c.) was added and the reaction mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath. Generally the bromination product crystallised from the solution. It was recrystallised from a suitable solvent. The results are described in Table I below.

Bromination by Liquid Bromine.—Liquid bromine (3 c.c.) was added to the requisite ester (2 g.) except in the case of *o*-cresyl ester when 6 c.c. of bromine were used. The mixture was shaken for half an hour and then left overnight. Water was then added to the reaction mixture when a solid was obtained. It was triturated with sodium bisulphite solution to remove excess of bromine and then crystallised from a suitable solvent. The results are described in Table II below.

Synthesis of the Bromination Products.—The compounds marked with asterisks in Tables I and II were also prepared by heating 3-bromo-5-nitrosalicylic acid (2 g.) and the requisite phenol (2 g.) in presence of phosphorus oxychloride (1 c.c.) at 120°-130° for half an hour. The compounds crystallised from the same solvent as those in Tables I and II.

Hydrolysis.—All bromination products were hydrolysed by using 50 c.c. of 0.5*N* potassium hydroxide solution for 1 g. of the substance and boiling the mixture for about 5 hours. The solution was then cooled in ice and carbon dioxide was passed through it when phenolic component separated. It was removed by extraction with ether. A quantity sufficient for purification and identification could be obtained only in the case of dibromo-*o*-cresyl 5-nitrosalicylate. The alkaline solution was then acidified with hydrochloric acid and the acid that separated was identified by mixed melting point with 5-nitrosalicylic acid or 3-bromo-5-nitrosalicylic acid.

TABLE I

N-S represents 5-nitrosalicylate; B-N-S represents 3-bromo-5-nitrosalicylate.

Esters used.	Period of heating.	Products obtained.	Crystallised from.	M. p.	Formula.	% Bromine. Found.	% Bromine. Calc.
1. Phenyl N-S.	3 hrs.	Phenyl B-N-S. *	Rect. spirit	164-65°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₅ NBr	23.8	23.7
2. 4-Bromo-phenyl N-S.	½	4-Bromophenyl B-N-S.*	Acetic acid	213-14°	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₅ NBr ₂	38.7	38.4
3. <i>o</i> -Cresyl N-S	4	<i>o</i> -Cresyl B-N-S.*	Acetic acid	154-55°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅ NBr	22.8	22.7
4. 5:6 (?) Dibromo- <i>o</i> -cresyl N-S.	4	5:6 (?) Dibromo- <i>o</i> -cresyl B-N-S.	Acetic acid	182-83°	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₅ NBr ₃	47.3	47.1
5. 4-Bromo- <i>o</i> -cresyl N-S.	2	4-Bromo- <i>o</i> -cresyl B-N-S. *	Acetic acid	190-91°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₅ NBr ₂	37.3	37.1
6. <i>m</i> -Cresyl N-S.	Time of keeping at room temp., 1 hr.	<i>m</i> -Cresyl B-N-S. *	Rect. spirit	112-13°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅ NBr	22.9	22.7
7. 2:4-Dibromo- <i>m</i> -cresyl N-S.	1 hr.	2:4-Dibromo- <i>m</i> -cresyl B-N-S. *†	Acetic acid	186-87°	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₅ NBr ₃	47.3	47.1
8. <i>p</i> -Cresyl N-S.	Overnight	<i>p</i> -Cresyl B-N-S.*	Acetic acid	152-53°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅ NBr	22.9	22.7
9. <i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl N-S.	Heated on a boiling water-bath, 2 hrs.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl B-N-S. *†	Acetic acid	178-89°	C ₁₃ H ₇ (O ₅) ₂ N ₂ Br	21.2	20.9
10. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl N-S.	2	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl B-N-S. *	Acetic acid	222-23°	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₇ N ₂ Br	21.1	20.9

† This substance is also obtained from *m*-cresyl and *p*-nitrophenyl N-S. (2 g.) and liquid bromine (6 c.c.) in presence of iodine catalyst.

TABLE II

N-S and B-N-S represent the same as in Table I.

Esters used.	Product obtained.	Crystallised from.	M. p.	Formula.	% Bromine	
					Found.	Calc.
1. Phenyl N-S.	4-Bromophenyl N-S.	Rect. spirit	157-58°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₅ NBr	23.6	23.7
2. Phenyl B-N-S.	4-Bromophenyl B-N-S.**	Acetic acid	113-14°	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₅ NBr ₂	38.2	38.4
3. <i>o</i> -Cresyl N-S.	5:6(?) -Dibromo- <i>o</i> -cresyl N-S.	Acetic acid	196-97°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₅ NBr ₂	37.4	37.1
4. <i>o</i> -Cresyl B-N-S.	5:6(?) -Dibromo- <i>o</i> -cresyl B-N-S.†	Acetic acid	182-83°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₅ NBr ₂	47.2	47.1
5. <i>m</i> -Cresyl N-S.	2:4-Dibromo- <i>m</i> -cresyl N-S.*	Rect. spirit	155-56°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₅ NBr ₂	37.3	37.1
6. <i>m</i> -Cresyl B-N-S.	2:4-Bromo- <i>m</i> -cresyl B-N-S.*	Acetic acid	176-77°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₅ NBr ₂	37.4	37.1
7. <i>p</i> -Cresyl N-S.	2:3- or 2:5-Dibromo- <i>p</i> -cresyl N-S.	Acetic acid	198-99°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₅ NBr ₂	37.4	37.1
8. <i>p</i> -Cresyl B-N-S.	2:3- or 2:5-Dibromo- <i>p</i> -cresyl B-N-S.	Acetic acid	170-72°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₅ NBr ₂	47.3	47.1

† Also obtained from simple aryl ester of N-S (2 g.) and liquid bromine (6 c.c.) in presence of iodine catalyst.

‡ Also obtained from *m*-cresyl N-S in acetic acid medium by heating on a boiling water-bath for 16 hours.

? This constitution is provisionally given as the melting point of the phenolic component is very near to that of 5:6-dibromo-*o*-cresol.